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**ON THE OCCURRENCE OF SURFACE SLICKS
IN THE OCEANS**

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Summary

This report contains the results from an investigation on the occurrence of *natural biogenic surface films* in different regions of the oceans. The objective was to quantitatively investigate their presence in different waters, trying to find a relation between their occurrence and their position referred to the distance from the coast (close to the coast, far from the coast, open ocean).

SAR images, collected during the two SIR-C/X-SAR missions in April and October 1994, have been used in the analysis. Today, the capability of the SAR to detect natural films on the ocean surface, is well documented. The main characteristics of the shuttle and its technical aspects of interest for this research, are presented in the first part of this report.

21 sites from different parts of the world, more or less intensively mapped by shuttle data, have been included in the study. These sites should offer a representative picture of regions, located at different latitudes and longitudes, for the two periods investigated. A list of the sites chosen is given in chapter 4. For each site, a list of the 'data-takes' which have been analyzed is given, and a map containing the location of the detected surface slicks is shown. Some brief comments are also added.

The results of the work have been summarized in the last chapter. In the Southern Hemisphere the occurrence of natural slicks seems to be much lower than in the Northern Hemisphere. Some areas, such as the North Sea, the Mediterranean, the Galapagos Islands, and the Philippines, have a particularly high occurrence of natural slicks close to land in April. The activity significantly decreases in the same regions in October, with the exception of the Philippines. In the open ocean only very few surface slicks have been detected, mainly in the Atlantic Ocean. On the other hand, in semi-enclosed basins their occurrence is more relevant. No clear trend has been found related to the season.

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1 Introduction

The objective of this work was to quantitatively investigate the presence of *natural biogenic surface films* in different regions of the oceans, trying to find a relation between their occurrence and their position referred to the distance from the coast (close to the coast, far from the coast, open ocean).

Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images were used in this research. It is well known that the SAR is able to detect the presence of natural slicks on the sea surface (Gade et al., 1997; Hovland et al., 1993; 1994, Espedal et al., 1995). The signature is a dark spot corresponding to a lower backscatter return, called a slick. The low radar return is caused by the damping action of natural films on sea surface ripples. These short waves are responsible for the radar return in SAR images (Donelan and Pierson, 1992, Hühnerfuss et al., 1983a and b).

A measure of the damping effect is the damping ratio, defined as the ratio between the backscatter in the presence of a surface slick and that of the surrounding clean sea surface. The damping ratio plotted as a function of the frequency has a 'resonance-like' behavior according to the Marangoni theory (Cini and Lombardini, 1978). The maximum is located in the C-band. Thus, this band has the highest radar contrast (between slick and slick-free signals). It is therefore believed that this frequency band gives the best results for natural slicks detection. Moreover, several laboratory experiments have shown that the radar contrast is lowest in the L-band. Therefore, in this band natural slicks may sometimes not be detected, because they are hidden by the wave pattern (Gade et al., 1996).

The presence of natural slick signatures in SAR images is also dependent on the polarization employed, and on the instrument sensitivity. The VV polarization gives a higher radar return compared to that of the HH polarization; i.e. the difference is around 2 dB (Gower et al, 1993). When the wind is low, the radar backscatter is lower and the radar return may be below the instrument noise threshold. In this case the image is useless for slick detection. Operating in the VV polarization allows to have a slightly higher noise threshold.

Several experiments have shown that the best SAR configuration for detecting natural slicks employs a C-band frequency and a VV polarization.

The detection of natural slicks is hampered by other features whose signature closely resembles that of natural slicks. This includes internal waves, region of low winds, oil spills, current shears, rain cells, or grease ice. Usually discrimination is possible after a more

detailed observation of the image: for example, internal waves give rise to dark signatures, whose shape (bright and dark parallel lines) is easily recognized.

On the other hand, in the case of oil spills, the signature is sometimes so similar to natural film, that auxiliary data are often required. These are e.g. wind information, current information, bathymetry or platform location (Espedal, 1998). For proper slick discrimination, a supervised algorithm has to be used. Such an algorithm includes both direct analysis (shape, size, damping, gradients and texture) of the slick, contextual analysis, and the use of SAR models and oil drift models (Espedal, 1998). However, in this work, the amount of data examined was huge. Discrimination was therefore based on some simple 'rules-of-thumb'. These rules were:

- Rain cells have a dark center surrounded by bright squall lines. Weather information will indicate if it rained.
- Internal waves are bright and dark parallel lines.
- Current shears have a bright or dark curving signature.
- Low wind speed areas have a very homogeneous large dark signature.
- Natural films are either large dark inhomogeneous signatures or smaller dark slicks.
- Large oil spills are reported and are therefore easy to identify. Smaller oil spills are usually narrow slicks from a ship or platform spill. If a bright spot (indicating the ship or platform) was seen near the slick, the slick was assumed to be an oil spill.

Finally, it must be remembered that a window of wind speed has been found (Scott, 1986) where the detection of natural slicks is possible. The lower threshold is connected to the SAR sensitivity problem explained before and is around 2-3 m/s. The higher threshold is due to the break down action caused by moderate to strong winds (> 7 m/s) on surface slicks, so that the natural films are washed down or their damping effect disappears in the noise of wind generated waves.

During the investigation, data collected in 1994 by the two SIR-C/X-SAR missions over different oceanography sites were analyzed. The fact that this shuttle was operating contemporary in 3 bands is helpful for the detection of natural slicks, since it allows to plot the damping ratio as a function of frequency. However, in this work, since the amount of data was extremely high, only the data from a single radar frequency have been analyzed.

21 regions located in different parts of the world were considered. The satellite coverage was more frequent in some of these areas, while it was considerably more sporadic in others. This has of course been taken into account when making the final considerations.

2 SIR-C/X-SAR

The SIR-C/X-SAR is the last of a group of satellites launched by NASA under the so called *Mission to Planet Earth*. Two missions of 10 days were completed at the beginning of April and October 1994: these two periods were chosen since they have relevant seasonal differences.

The shuttle was the first satellite carrying a multi-frequency radar operating simultaneously in the L, C and X band and with different polarization. Among other things, this has allowed to validate the multi-frequency and multi-polarization imaging models developed in the last years for different oceanographic phenomena.

The relative low altitude of the orbit, approximately 215 km, has been particularly advantageous in the oceanographic investigations, since it has increased the range of ocean waves reliably imaged by the SAR instruments compared to the other high orbit satellites. Besides, this choice allowed a slight westwards drift in the equatorial crossing longitude in the one day repeat orbit so that many sites were imaged at very different incidence angles. Finally, the daily repeat orbit has been proved to be well fit to the dynamics of most of the oceanographic phenomena.

During the second flight the shuttle was able to fly nearly the same orbit as the first flight: therefore, a significant amount of data was collected which allowed repeat interferometric SAR processing.

Around 400 sites were imaged: 19 had a higher priority (the so-called 'supersites') and other 15 ('backup supersites') were chosen to substitute the firsts, if necessary. The total coverage of the shuttle during the two missions is shown in fig.1.

Figure 1: Ground coverage of the 2 missions.

2.1 The Shuttle Payload

The shuttle payload consists of two radars: the SIR-C/X-SAR. The main characteristics of the two are summarized in Table 1.

The SIR-C is a multi-polarization (HH, VV, HV and VH), multi-frequency radar, operating in the L- ($\lambda_R = 23.5$ cm, $f_R = 1.25$ GHz) as well as in the C-band ($\lambda_R = 5.8$ cm, $f_R = 5.3$ GHz). It has been the first satellite able to transmit and receive contemporary in two different bands and to vary the transmitted and received polarization.

This was made possible employing two active phased-array antennae. The two beams were formed by hundreds of transmitters embedded in the radar antenna surface. By properly adjusting the energy of these transmitters the beam could be electronically steered without moving the antenna. Such a solution together with the roll and yaw maneuvers of the shuttle, has allowed to acquire the images with an incidence angle varying from 20° to 60° , $\pm 20^\circ$ from the nominal position of 40° off the nadir.

Parameter	L-Band	C-Band	X-Band
Wavelength (cm)	23.5	5.8	3.1
Frequency (GHz)	1.25	5.3	9.6
Polarization	HH, VV, HV, VH	HH, VV, HV, VH	VV
Spatial Resolution (m)	13-26	13-26	10 - 20
Look-Angle	$20^\circ - 60^\circ$	$20^\circ - 60^\circ$	$17^\circ - 63^\circ$
Swath Width (km)	$15 \times 90 - 15 \times 60$	$15 \times 90 - 15 \times 60$	$15 \times 90 - 15 \times 60$
Bandwidth (MHz)	10 - 20	10 - 20	10 - 20

Table 1. SIR-C/X-SAR System Characteristics.

The X-SAR is a single polarization (VV) radar, operating in the X-band ($\lambda_R = 3.1$ cm, $f_R = 9.6$ GHz). The antenna was a planar slotted waveguide array, mounted on a support structure which was mechanically tilted in order to align the narrow, pencil-thin beam with those of the SIR-C. The incidence angles varied from 17° to 63° , 23° from the nominal position.

The SIR-C and the X-SAR were synchronized in order to have identical imaging geometry, thus allowing a comparison of the radar signatures in the 3 bands. However, each radar system could also operate autonomously. The transmit bandwidth could be changed, thereby making the range resolution variable.

2.2 The noise equivalent sigma zero

The SIR-C/X-SAR was designed in order to have a sufficient system sensitivity: this is specified in terms of the noise equivalent sigma zero (σ^0), defined as the surface backscattering coefficient corresponding to a signal to noise ratio equal to 1.

The planned value for an incidence angle of 50° and operating in low resolution mode are:

- - 40 dB for the L-Band
- - 35 dB for the C-Band
- - 22 dB for the X-Band.

If these values are confirmed in practice, then the threshold value of wind above which the detection is possible should increase. For example, the value of σ^0 was planned to be around -27 dB for the ERS SAR (operating in the C-Band, VV polarization) leading to a wind threshold of around 3 m/s; for the RADARSAT (operating in the same band, but HH polarization) the value of σ^0 was expected to be circa 2 dB higher, due to the lower return caused by operating in the horizontal polarization.

If this higher sensitivity of the SIR-C/X-SAR is confirmed, then the window of wind velocities inside which the detection of natural surface slicks is possible would increase. As a matter of fact, the higher threshold value does not depend on the instrument sensitivity, but on the fact that at this high to moderate wind conditions the film is washed down or its effect is hidden in the noise of wind generated waves. On the other hand, low wind conditions are ideal for the generation of surface slicks.

3 Availability of data

The analysis has been based on the images either provided by the DLR through its web site (address: <http://www.dfd.dlr.de>) or stored on the JPL CD_ROM. Both these two types of data are Survey Product. They serve as quick-looks of the areas imaged by the shuttle, but they do not contain any quantitative information (for example, they are not calibrated). On the other hand, since the aim of the research was focused on retrieving statistical information about the occurrence of surface slicks, the main point was that the image quality was good enough to allow the detection of dark spots caused by surface slicks.

The DLR site provided only X-SAR images. This band and the polarization employed (VV) can be considered suitable for the detection of natural slicks. The images have been processed before being stored in the web site. If this has been helpful in improving the signatures of surface features in the open ocean, it has, on the other hand hampered their detection close to the coast. Here, land was often the main focus, at the expense of the sea. Besides, little information about the images (incidence angle, spatial resolution, date, time) were displayed.

The data on the CD-ROM contains much more technical information. On the other hand, all the images analyzed were in the L-band and a good part in the HH polarization, which is considered the worst configuration for natural slicks detection.

3.1 The Data-Takes

The SIR-C/X-SAR data have been acquired in units of so-called "data takes". These are named by the major test site. They may be thousands as well as few tens kilometers long and therefore span whole continents or very limited regions. The test sites have been monitored several times on ascending and descending orbits, with different radar parameters (like incidence angle and spatial resolution).

All test sites have been assigned a 3 character Site ID. The first character indicates the primary discipline of the investigation: C for calibration, E for ecology, G for geology, H for hydrology, M for electromagnetic theory, N for oceanography and T for targets of opportunity. The second character is used to distinguish a Supersite (S) from a Backup Supersite (B) or from a Non Supersite (any other character). The third character distinguishes between different site coverage.

4 The choice of the different sites

The 21 sites were selected trying to cover the most different parts of the ocean, according to the SIR-C/X-SAR coverage. The goal was to have the most homogeneous distribution as possible for the different latitudes and longitudes. Except for the regions at high latitudes in the Southern Hemisphere, this goal has been reached.

In some areas, such as in the mid latitude regions for both the Southern and Northern Hemisphere, several different coastal sites were covered by the SIR-C/X-SAR. In these cases, a choice had to be made. This may have favored sites which could later have been discovered to have an insignificant biogenic activity at the expense of other sites which might have a higher activity. But this choice had to be made in order to have a treatable number of data.

Unfortunately, some sites were not sufficiently covered by the space shuttle. The results should be verified further in the future. On the other hand, other sites were covered more frequently, so that the total amount of images was huge. In such cases, only a part of the available data takes has been selected. The criteria were that the data should cover repeated orbits and be distributed over several days.

The 21 sites, divided according to their latitudinal position, are listed in the tables below.

Table 2: High Latitude Sites, Northern Hemisphere.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
1. Alaska Sea	45 N -> 65 N	130 W -> 160 W
2. North Atlantic	40 N -> 60 N	10 W -> 45 W
3. North Sea	50 N -> 60 N	5 W -> 25 E
4. Okhotsk Sea	45 N -> 60 N	140 E -> 165 E

Table 3: Mid Latitude Sites, Northern Hemisphere.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
5. Gulf Stream	25 N -> 40 N	65 W -> 80 W
6. Mediterranean Sea	30 N -> 45 N	5 E -> 25 E
7. Japan Sea	25 N -> 45 N	120 E -> 140 E
8. Hawaii	10 N -> 30 N	145 W -> 165 W
9. Mexico Gulf	10 N -> 35 N	75 W -> 95 W

Table 4: Equatorial Sites.

LATITUDE	LONGITUDE	
10. Red Sea	10 N -> 25 N	35 E -> 45 E
11. Pacific Survey	10 S -> 15 N	140 W -> 170 W
12. Galapagos Islands	10 S -> 10 N	80 W -> 100 W
13. Gulf of Guinea	5 S -> 5 N	15 W -> 5 E
14. Indian Ocean	0 N -> 10 N	75 E -> 85 E
15. Philippines	10 S -> 25 N	110 E -> 130 E

Table 5: Mid Latitude Sites, Southern Hemisphere.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
16. Brazil	20 S -> 5 N	30 W -> 50 W
17. Chile	15 S -> 35 S	65 W -> 80 W
18. South Africa	10 S -> 50 S	10 E -> 50 E
19. Australian Current	25 S -> 40 S	150 E -> 160 E

Table 6: High Latitude Sites, Southern Hemisphere.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
20. South America	40 S -> 60 S	55 W -> 85 W
21. Weddel Sea	50 S -> 60 S	0 E -> 20 E

5 The 21 sites

In the following subsections, each site is analyzed in detail.

First, all the data-takes are listed with their main technical characteristics: the date and time, the number, the name of the location, the ID code, the polarization, the incidence angle, and the number of quick-looks analyzed. The data takes from DLR can be recognized because they are from the X-SAR (X-band, VV polarization), while those from JPL are from the SIR-C, L band.

After the list of data-takes, a brief comment is made concerning the site coverage and its slick activity in April and October. Finally, the map with the locations of natural surface slicks is attached.

5.1 Site #1 - Alaska Gulf

10/04	18:26	022.14	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	36.8	15
	19:58	023.02	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	36.6	11
12/04	19:21	055.02	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	32.9	15
13/10	19:01	071.02	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	30.9	16
15/04	18:20	103.01	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	L-HH	28.6	21
16/04	16:27	118.02	NE Pacific Ocean A2	N37	X-VV	29.9	22
18/04	14:13	149.02	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	L-HH	36.1	21
01/10	18:37	022.14	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	37.2	15
	20:09	023.20	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	36.9	15
02/10	19:52	039.20	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	35.1	8
04/10	19:12	071.10	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	30.9	5
06/10	17:10	102.20	NE Pacific Ocean A2	N37	X-VV	39.8	15
07/10	16:27	118.10	Top Orbit/Interferometry	GF2	X-VV	47.2	10
08/10	16:19	134.10	Top Orbit/Interferometry	GF2	X-VV	47.3	11
09/10	15:56	150.10	Top Orbit/Interferometry	GF2	X-VV	47.3	10

April: no surface slicks have been detected.

October: two regions presenting a low activity, have been found in the same day (data takes 022.14 and 023.20), at a certain distance from the coast. However, in the following days no other surface slicks have been detected. There is one suspicious signature in data take 149.02, which could be due to natural slicks. No activity at all has been found close to the coast.

5.2 Site #2 - North Atlantic

10/04	14:05	019.02	EN Atlantic A	NS5	X-VV	39.2	33
11/04	07:40	031.01	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	39.7	15
12/04	07:21	047.01	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	31.0	23
13/04	07:02	063.01	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	22.1	16
14/04	06:42	079.01	EN Atlantic C	NS7	X-VV	24.7	20
15/04	06:23	095.03	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	30.0	11
16/04	12:08	115.05	EN Atlantic E	NS9	X-VV	24.0	32
17/04	05:41	127.01	EN Atlantic F	NSX	X-VV	20.8	15
18/04	05:18	143.01	EN Atlantic G	NSY	X-VV	28.0	20
01/10	14:16	019.20	EN Atlantic A	NS5	X-VV	29.8	33
02/10	07:51	031.10	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	39.3	14
03/10	07:32	047.11	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	30.8	35
04/10	07:13	063.10	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	21.3	16
05/10	06:55	079.10	EN Atlantic C	NS7	X-VV	24.6	11
06/10	06:34	095.30	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	30.2	12
07/10	12:20	115.50	EN Atlantic E	NS9	X-VV	27.0	35
08/10	05:51	127.00	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	39.7	13
09/10	05:28	143.00	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	39.8	12
10/10	05:25	159.00	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	39.8	11

The North Atlantic was marked as an oceanographic supersite and, thus, several data takes have been obtained.

April: a large number of surface slicks have been detected, though their presence is not constant during the period. As a matter of fact, no activity at all is found from April 13th to 15th and in the last two days. This may be due to strong winds which may have blown for some days and been absent in others. The surface slicks seem to be concentrated in well defined regions: mainly between 19° and 26° West and 43° and 47° North and around 30° West and 50° North;

October: the activity seems to be even higher than in April, though again not constant. As a matter of fact, during the last five days of October (from 6th to 10th) no surface slicks at all have been revealed. Also in this case the activity seems to be concentrated in a well defined region located between 17° and 26° West and 45° and 48° North. This is about the same area as in April.

5.3 Site # 3 - North Sea

10/04	09:35	016.12	Stauning, Denmark (1)	G65	X-VV	30.1	14
11/04	10:49	033.05	Stauning, Denmark (1)	G65	X-VV	36.9	16
12/04	07:21	047.01	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	31.0	17
13/04	07:06	063.02	North Sea A1	NBB	X-VV	35.3	11
14/04	08:20	080.03	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	40.3	18
15/04	07:53	096.03	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	48.5	14
16/04	07:33	112.02	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	29.9	20
17/04	05:45	127.02	Thetford, England	E66	X-VV	46.5	30
01/10	09:46	016.12	Stauning, Denmark (1)	G65	X-VV	30.1	11
02/10	11:00	033.50	Stauning, Denmark (1)	G65	X-VV	36.8	17
03/10	07:32	047.11	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	30.8	6
04/10	07:18	063.10	North Sea A1	NBB	X-VV	38.3	20
05/10	08:30	080.10	North Sea Slick	N45	X-VV	44.3	32
06/10	08:05	096.20	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	44.0	10
07/10	07:45	112.20	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	43.2	29
08/10	07:28	128.20	Rugen Island, Germany	H02	X-VV	46.3	27
09/10	07:05	144.20	Rugen Island, Germany	H02	X-VV	45.7	40
10/10	06:42	160.20	Rugen Island, Germany	H02	X-VV	46.2	28

April: several surface slicks have been detected, especially on the west side of the Danish coast, both close as well as far from the coast. The activity is also good close to the German coast. This region is known to have strong mesoscale processes, called eddies. Some eddies have, in fact, been detected (data takes 047.01 and 112.02). They can accumulate natural film, with a vortex shape, following the eddy orbital movement direction (Dokken and Wahl, 1996; Johannessen, 1993). Moreover, the North Sea is highly trafficked and there are several oil platforms, located especially close to the German coast. This region is subject to a high degree of oil pollution. A few slicks, closely resembling natural slicks but assumed to be caused by oil spills, have been detected. In most of these cases the dark slicks were associated with bright spots representing oil platforms or ships.

October: no surface slicks have been detected in the first 7 days, while afterwards a good activity was found. The activity was concentrated far from the coast. Again, some oil spills were detected.

5.4 Site # 4 - Sea of Okhotsk

11/04	00:25	026.04	Karymsky, Kamchatka	G62	X-VV	35.3	18
11/04	22:35	041.02	Tolbechik, Kamchatka	G34	X-VV	29.9	21
12/04	00:05	042.02	Karymsky, Kamchatka	G62	X-VV	32.2	29
12/04	01:38	043.03	Sea of Okhotsk A0	N48	X-VV	26.8	19
13/04	01:19	059.02	Sea of Okhotsk A2	N50	X-VV	26.8	25
13/04	23:27	074.03	Sea of Okhotsk A2	N50	L-VV	28.1	13
15/04	22:46	106.20	Sea of Okhotsk A2	N50	L-VV	28.4	13
17/04	22:05	138.02	Bezymienny, Kamchatka	G40	X-VV	38.4	21
01/10	00:53	010.10	Karymsky, Kamchatka	G62	L-VH	41.1	18
03/10	22:26	057.20	Tolbechik, Kamchatka	G34	L-VH	34.2	16
06/10	19:56	104.30	Kliuchevskai, Kamchatka	G08	L-HH	28.3	13
07/10	20:51	121.10	Kliuchevskai2, Kamchatka	GCI	L-VV	31.3	20
09/10	20:06	153.10	Kliuchevskai2, Kamchatka	GCI	L-VV	31.3	20

April: the region was mainly covered by ice, especially close to the Khabarovsk Kray coast. Here several dark areas have been detected, which were probably due to grease ice. Only a very few natural slicks have been found, mainly close to the Kamchatka peninsula.

October: in this case the ice was not yet formed. Many surface slicks have been detected, particularly in the stripe between 54° and 57° North, far from the coast.

5.5 Site # 5 - Gulf Stream

10/04	18:39	022.03	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	46.4	15
12/04	18:01	054.02	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	L-HH	32.8	16
13/04	17:34	070.01	Gulf Stream A1	NS1	L-VV	33.6	10
14/04	17:23	086.05	Gulf Stream A1	NS1	L-HH	38.6	12
16/04	16:42	118.07	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	L-VV	25.6	15
17/04	16:21	134.05	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	30.0	23
01/10	18:50	022.30	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	36.5	14
03/10	18:12	054.30	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	50.7	34
05/10	17:34	086.50	Gulf Stream A1	NS1	L-HH	21.4	12
07/10	16:55	118.33	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	39.5	15
08/10	16:32	134.33	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	39.5	15
09/10	16:09	150.33	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	39.5	15
10/10	15:46	166.52	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	27.2	15

April: the activity is not constant, so there is an alternation of days having a medium activity with others showing no activity at all. It is not possible to define any region where the surface slicks preferably occur. However, they have not been detected close to the coast.

October: far from the coast the activity seems to be more intense than in April, while it remains null close to the coast. Like in April, the surface slicks are not located in one precise area.

5.6 Site # 6 - Mediterranean Sea

10/04	12:43	018.22	Matera, Italy	CB1	L-HH	16.4	11
11/04	12:25	034.32	Matera, Italy	CB1	V-HH	32.6	12
13/04	11:47	066.42	Matera, Italy	CB1	V-HH	50.0	14
17/04	02:36	125.02	Matera, Italy	CB1	L-HH	19.1	10
18/04	02:20	141.12	Matera, Italy	CB1	L-HH	23.3	7
19/04	01:57	157.00	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	L-HH	55.9	12
20/04	01:34	173.10	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	L-HH	57.0	10
01/10	05:10	013.11	Central Greece	T83	X-VV	34.2	4
01/10	12:54	018.22	Matera, Italy	CB1	X-VV	19.1	18
04/10	04:12	061.10	Matera, Italy	CB1	X-VV	22.8	13
04/10	11:58	066.32	Strait of Sicily	N57	X-VV	51.1	13
07/10	10:58	114.50	Monastir, Tunisia	G91	X-VV	57.5	11
08/10	02:52	125.10	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	X-VV	47.6	22
09/10	02:29	141.10	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	X-VV	47.6	19
10/10	02:06	157.10	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	X-VV	47.6	20

April: many surface slicks have been found close to the coast, spread on several areas. Far from the coast the activity seems to be negligible.

October: the activity is still good close to the coast. Far from the coast, several natural slicks have been found, particularly in the Sicilian Channel.

5.7 Site # 7 - Japan Sea

10/04	05:19	013.03	Japan A0	N66	X-VV	27.2	26
11/04	05:01	029.05	Japan C3	N79	X-VV	45.9	42
12/04	04:43	045.03	Japan A1	N67	X-VV	36.6	17
13/04	04:23	061.04	Japan A0	N66	X-VV	27.8	19
14/04	04:05	077.04	Japan A4	N70	X-VV	25.7	20
01/10	05:30	013.30	Japan A0	N66	L-HH	29.1	17
					X-VV	27.7	1
02/10	05:12	029.50	Japan A2	N68	L-HH	49.9	26
03/10	04:53	045.40	Japan A1	N67	L-HH	40.3	21
04/10	04:34	061.40	Japan A0	N66	X-VV	26.9	24
05/10	04:16	077.40	Japan A4	N70	L-HH	27.7	15

April: a good activity is constantly present close to the Japan coast. Far from the coast the activity is negligible, with the exception of April 11th, when some surface slicks have been found in the region centered around 40°N and 132°E.

October: while close to the coast the situation is similar to that of April, many more surface slicks have been detected far from the coast, both in the Japan Sea as well as in the Pacific Ocean.

5.8 Site # 8 - Hawaii

12/04	14:37	052.01	Hawaii	BG0	X-VV	49.5	11
13/04	14:17	068.00	Hawaii	GB0	X-VV	56.7	40
16/04	13:16	116.01	Blue Hawaii	N04	X-VV	26.9	21
17/04	12:55	132.02	Blue Hawaii	N04	X-VV	26.9	21
18/04	12:33	148.00	Blue Hawaii	N04	X-VV	35.4	21
03/10	14:48	052.10	Kilauca, Hawaii	GB0	X-VV	49.3	16
04/10	14:28	068.00	Kilauca, Hawaii	GB0	X-VV	56.6	40
07/10	13:28	116.10	Blue Hawaii	N04	L-HH	29.3	17
08/10	22:29	138.40	Pu'u O'o, Hawaii	G10	X-VV	58.5	25
10/10	21:43	170.40	Pu'u O'o, Hawaii	G10	X-VV	58.5	22

April: no activity at all.

October: no activity at all.

5.9 Site # 9 - Gulf of Mexico

11/04	19:53	039.04	Gulf of Mexico 1	N07	X-VV	39.8	22
12/04	19:35	055.05	Gulf of Mexico 0	N06	X-VV	39.8	7
13/04	09:54	065.02	Gulf of Mexico	N06	X-VV	27.4	10
	19:16	071.05	Gulf of Mexico 3	N09	X-VV	44.8	6
14/04	09:30	081.00	Chulchece, Yucatan Mex	E58	X-VV	24.5	17
02/10	20:02	039.40	Gulf of Mexico 1	N07	X-VV	39.8	36
04/10	19:26	071.50	Gulf of Mexico 3	N09	X-VV	44.7	29
07/10	18:23	119.30	20MHz D/L over N.Amer	GF8	X-VV	47.3	21
09/10	17:37	151.30	20MHz D/L over N.Amer	GF8	X-VV	47.3	20

The Gulf of Mexico is known for presenting several oil seepages whose signatures in SAR images closely resemble those of natural slicks. Some attention must then be paid in order to not confuse the two surface features. Besides, several images contained bright spots, since this region has a high naval traffic. Thus, some dark spots may be due to oil slicks.

April: the activity is mainly concentrated far from the coast, in the region centered at 26°N and 87°W. However, it is never particularly high, though constant for all the days. One slick has been detected close to Cuba coast (data takes 055.05).

October: the situation is mainly identical to April, though far from the coast the activity is slightly more intense and seems to be more scattered.

Gulf of Mexico – April

Gulf of Mexico – October

5.10 Site # 10 - Red Sea

10/04	01:53	011.01	Saudi Arabia D(1) 4	GOX	X-VV	35.0	3
11/04	01:35	027.01	Saudi Arabia A(1) 0	GB4	X-VV	42.4	3
13/04	00:56	059.01	Saudi Arabia C(2) 4	GB5	X-VV	46.5	4
14/04	00:33	075.04	Mabira, Uganda	E33	X-VV	28.8	4
15/04	00:18	091.03	Saudi Arabia D(1) 2	GB8	X-VV	54.6	3
15/04	23:58	107.03	Saudi Arabia D(1) 2	GB8	L-HH	54.6	4
01/10	02:04	011.10	Saudi Arabia C(1) 4	GOX	L-HH	44.1	3
04/10	01:05	059.62	Saudi Arabia C(2) 4	GB5	L-HH	43.2	5
05/10	00:44	075.40	Mabira, Uganda	E33	L-HH	29.3	4
07/10	00:09	107.30	Saudi Arabia D(1) 2	GB8	L-HH	57.6	
09/10	22:50	154.90	Konjoke Res. Ctr. Rwanda	T03	X-VV	25.1	6

The region has been covered for a sufficient number of days (5) both in April and October. Unfortunately, the data takes were taken across, and not along, the Red Sea, often in its most narrow part. Therefore, only a few images were available.

April: the slick activity is quite high, both close as well as far from the coast.

October: same as April.

Red Sea – April

Red Sea – October

5.11 Site # 11 - Equatorial Pacific Ocean

10/04	02:31	011.04	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX3	X-VV	28.4	29
13/04	12:41	066.09	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX6	X-VV	27.8	27
14/04	21:58	089.03	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX9	X-VV	27.3	26
15/04	23:06	106.03	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NXD	X-VV	27.3	29
17/04	09:51	129.09	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX9	X-VV	26.9	29
01/10	02:41	011.40	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX3	X-VV	26.8	26
02/10	12:02	133.20	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX8	X-VV	26.8	31
04/10	12:52	066.20	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX6	X-VV	27.4	31
05/10	23:17	106.40	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NXD	X-VV	26.9	32
06/10	09:16	162.00	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NXG	X-VV	26.9	31
10/10	01:29	075.70	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX3	X-VV	33.2	33

April: no surface slicks have been detected, except from the data take 106.03.

October: the activity seems to be very intense, though not constant through all the days. This may suggest that in the days where no surface slicks have been detected the wind was too strong.

5.12 Site # 12 - Galapagos Islands

11/04	21:29	040.05	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	21.0	28
14/04	20:32	088.06	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	34.0	11
15/04	20:11	104.07	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	46.0	18
17/04	19:28	136.03	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	52.4	40
02/10	21:40	040.50	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	22.4	22
04/10	21:02	072.70	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	22.8	20
05/10	20:43	088.60	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	46.0	14
06/10	20:22	104.70	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	53.3	16
07/10	20:02	120.70	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	53.9	21
08/10	19:39	136.70	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	54.0	18

April: there is an excellent activity close to the islands, while no surface slicks have been detected in the open ocean.

October: no surface slick has been detected.

5.13 Site # 13 - Gulf of Guinea

11/04	15:28	036.07	Sahel 0	EX3	L-HH	36.5	5
12/04	15:15	052.05	Sahel	EX4	L-HH	36.3	4
17/04	13:29	132.08	Sahel	EXD	L-HH	37.0	12
02/10	15:39	036.70	Sahel	EX3	X-VV	34.9	6
03/10	15:26	052.50	Sahel	EX4	X-VV	35.4	4
07/10	14:02	116.50	Sahel	EXB	X-VV	35.3	6
08/10	13:39	132.30	W.America fix 45	GF7	X-VV	44.7	13
09/10	02:19	140.90	Tilemsi, Sahara Mali	G53	L-VV	46.8	5
10/10	01:56	156.90	Tilemsi, Sahara Mali	G53	L-VV	47.1	7

The coverage is limited to the coastal region and is quite poor in April.

April: no surface slicks.

October: no surface slicks.

5.14 Site # 14 - Indian Ocean

08/10	07:28	128.20	Rugen Island, Germany	HO2	X-VV	46.3	18
09/10	07:05	144.20	Rugen Island, Germany	HO2	X-VV	45.7	25
10/10	06:42	160.20	Rugen Island, Germany	HO2	X-VV	46.2	3

In April this region was not covered by any data take. In October, the coverage is also limited, both concerning the number of the days (only 3) as well as the distance from the coast.

October: a few surface slicks located approximately in the same region (the only one imaged by the shuttle), at a certain distance from the coast.

5.15 Site # 15 - Philippines

12/04	06:20	046.03	Western Pacific 11	CSK	X-VV	57.5	57
14/04	05:39	078.03	Pinatubo, Philippines	G98	X-VV	51.3	28
16/04	04:57	110.03	Western Pacific 3	CSC	X-VV	55.3	59
08/10	04:38	126.30	Pinatubo, Philippines	G98	X-VV	29.6	30
09/10	04:16	142.30	Pinatubo, Philippines	G98	X-VV	29.6	30
10/10	03:53	158.30	Pinatubo, Philippines	G98	X-VV	29.6	30

Though only a few days have been considered, the results can be considered significant.

April: good activity, concentrated around the Philippines. No surface slick has been found in the open ocean.

October: close to the coast the activity is even more intense than before and is extended to Indonesia. Far from the coast it is still negligible.

Philippines Sea— October

5.16 Site # 16 - Brazil

14/04	17:35	086.06	Bebedouro, Brazil	HSI	X-VV	47.3	16
15/04	17:14	102.06	Bebedouro, Brazil	HSI	X-VV	53.2	10
30/09	19:19	006.30	Bebedouro, Brazil	HSI	X-VV	45.8	25
02/10	18:47	038.60	Bahia, Brazil	T33	L-HH	51.0	9
05/10	17:46	086.60	Bebedouro, Brazil	HSI	X-VV	47.1	14
07/10	17:04	118.50	South America fix a45	GF3	L-VV	47.1	18
09/10	16:18	150.50	South America fix a45	GF3	L-VV	47.1	18
10/10	15:55	166.80	South America fix a45	GF3	L-VV	47.1	18

The coverage is quite poor in April (only 2 days) and limited to coastal areas.

April: no surface slick has been detected.

October: the data are varying. Some days there is some activity, while in others no surface slick has been found. However, the overall activity is very low.

5.17 Site # 17 - North Chile

10/04	21:57	021.08	Cerro Aroncagua, Argent	GON	X-VV	49.7	7
12/04	07:01	046.05	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	X-VV	28.8	6
14/04	06:21	078.06	Amason Calibration	CXH	X-VV	28.8	12
	20:40	088.07	San Juan, Argentina	GOA	X-VV	41.4	7
15/04	06:03	094.07	Menaus CSAP, Brazil	ES2	L-HH	26.3	7
16/04	05:42	110.05	Menaus Cabakiane, Brazil	ES1	L-HH	27.4	6
18/04	05:00	142.05	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	L-HH	49.9	4
30/09	22:26	008.70	San Juan, Argentina	GOA	X-VV	37.3	7
01/10	22:08	024.80	Cerro Aroncagua, Argent	GON	X-VV	49.6	7
03/10	07:12	046.50	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	X-VV	30.1	6
05/10	06:32	078.60	Amason Calibration	CXH	X-VV	30.4	12
	20:51	088.70	San Juan, Argentina	GOA	X-VV	41.1	6
07/10	05:53	110.50	Menaus Cabakiane, Brazil	ES1	X-VV	30.9	11
09/10	05:09	142.80	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	X-VV	43.8	8
10/10	04:46	158.80	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	X-VV	43.9	6

The coverage is mainly limited to coastal regions.

April: several slicks have been found close to the coast, around 20°S.

October: as in April, the activity seems to be limited to the same coastal regions.

5.18 Site # 18 - South Africa

11/04	15:43	036.08	Roter Kamm, Namibia 1	G68	L-HH	25.5	8
13/04	13:33	067.07	Kruger National Park, SA	E23	X-VV	55.2	6
17/04	21:29	137.07	Southern Africa	N53	L-VV	38.6	13
02/10	00:05	025.50	Mozambique Channel	TB3	X-VV	48.3	19
04/10	13:44	067.70	Kruger National Park, SA	E13	X-VV	55.1	6
06/10	22:23	105.90	Southern Africa	N53	L-HH	28.8	43
07/10	11:13	114.60	Mozambique Channel	TB3	L-VV	50.7	10
09/10	21:17	153.60	Southern Africa	N53	L-HH	28.4	34
10/10	11:19	163.50	Sahel	EX2	X-VV	45.3	25

April: no surface slick has been detected.

October: the data cover a wider region than in April. In the area imaged also in April there is no surface slick. Some slicks are instead found in the North-West coast of Mozambique, at latitudes close to Equator.

5.19 Site # 19 - Australian Current

11/04	06:51	030.03	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	37.0	12
12/04	06:32	046.04	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	37.2	9
14/04	05:53	078.05	Australian Current	NO2	X-VV	26.8	11
18/04	03:00	141.07	Norfolk Island,Austr.	N43	X-VV	54.4	19
20/04	03:46	174.40	Sydney, Australia	T18	L-VV	31.3	9
02/10	07:02	030.40	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	37.3	12
03/10	06:43	046.40	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	37.2	19
05/10	06:04	078.40	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	28.8	11
08/10	04:57	126.40	Australian Fox a45	GFI	X-VV	45.2	30
09/10	04:34	142.40	Australian Fox a45	GFI	X-VV	45.3	30
10/10	04:11	158.40	Australian Fox a45	GFI	X-VV	45.3	30

April: no surface slicks.

October: no surface slicks.

5.20 Site # 20 - South America

11/04	23:13	041.05	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	44.2	14
12/04	05:22	045.06	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	48.8	19
13/04	05:04	061.07	Cerro Cumbre	GSK	X-VV	47.6	6
14/04	04:45	077.07	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	53.4	5
17/04	21:12	137.03	Puerto Aisen	GSJ	X-VV	39.5	17
18/04	03:22	141.09	Cerro Cumbre	GSK	X-VV	54.8	4
01/10	00:01	009.40	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	54.2	12
	06:11	013.60	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	38.0	11
	23:42	025.30	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	L-HH	49.7	15
02/10	23:24	041.50	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	L-HH	32.5	12
03/10	22:46	057.50	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	L-HH	39.8	12
04/10	05:15	061.70	Cerro Cumbre	GSK	X-VV	48.4	5
	22:46	073.30	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	L-HH	32.5	11
06/10	04:36	093.70	Cerro Cumbre	GSK	L-HH	65.3	6
07/10	04:15	109.70	Puerto Aisen	GSJ	X-VV	48.3	6

April: no surface slicks.

October: a good activity is found far from the coast on October 3rd and 7th. The other days it looks like the wind is quite strong.

5.21 Site # 21 - Weddel Sea

01/10	20:51	023.60	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	22.8	24
02/10	20:32	039.90	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	20.3	33
03/10	20:13	055.80	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	30.4	31
04/10	19:54	071.80	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	29.9	21
06/10	19:14	103.80	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	28.7	31
07/10	18:53	119.50	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	22.8	35

Coverage: no data in April; good in October (6 days).

October: during the first days the area is mainly covered by ice, while in the last two data takes the spatial coverage is significantly reduced. No surface slick has been detected. Some attention must be paid to some dark features which closely resemble natural slick, but which are more likely to be grease ice.

6 Final Results

The results of the investigation are summarized in the tables below. For each site a letter has been assigned, when possible, referring to its slick activity: **N** for negligible, **VL** for very low, **L** for low, **M** for medium, **H** for high, **VH** for very high. Of course, this classification is subjective, but the author believes this gives a representative picture of the situation. A more statistical approach, for example based on the percentage of images containing natural slicks, is not applicable in this case: as a matter of fact, the degree of activity may vary considerably in different images and this must be taken in to account.

Moreover, some images may contain only one or a few dark spots, whose origin is not clear. They may be due to biogenic activity, but they may be also caused by man-made pollution. Their discrimination is not always possible and a more detailed analysis requires wind information and other means of help which are extremely time consuming for such an extensive research.

For high latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	Alaska Gulf N	North Sea VH	Sea of Okhotsk L
Far (A)	Alaska Gulf N	North Sea VH	Sea of Okhotsk N
Open Ocean (A)		Atlantic Ocean M	
Coast (O)	Alaska Gulf N	North Sea L	Sea of Okhotsk VL
Far (O)	Alaska Gulf VL	North Sea M	Sea of Okhotsk VH
Open Ocean (O)		Atlantic Ocean H	

For mid latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	Gulf of Mexico VL Gulf Stream N	Mediterranean Sea H	Japan Sea M
Far (A)	Gulf of Mexico M Gulf Stream M	Mediterranean Sea VL	Japan Sea M
Open Ocean (A)	Hawaii VL		
Coast (O)	Gulf of Mexico N Gulf Stream N	Mediterranean Sea M	Japan Sea M
Far (O)	Gulf of Mexico M Gulf Stream H	Mediterranean Sea VH	Japan Sea VH
Open Ocean (O)	Hawaii N		

For the Equator regions:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	Galapagos Islands VH	Red Sea M Guinea N	Philippines H
Far (A) Open Ocean (A)	Galapagos Islands VL Pacific Ocean VL Galapagos Islands N	Red Sea M	Philippines VL Philippines N
Coast (O)	Galapagos Islands N	Red Sea M Guinea N	Indian Ocean N Philippines VH
Far (O)	Galapagos Islands N	Red Sea M	Indian Ocean VL Philippines VL
Open Ocean (O)	Pacific Ocean M Galapagos Islands N		Philippines N

For mid latitudes in the Southern Hemisphere:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	Brazil N North Chile H	South Africa N	Australian Current N
Far (A) Open Ocean (A)	Brazil N North Chile L		Australian Current N
Coast (O)	Brazil N North Chile H	South Africa N	Australian Current N
Far (O)	Brazil VL North Chile L	South Africa N	Australian Current N
Open Ocean (O)			

For high latitudes in the Southern Hemisphere:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A) Far (A) Open Ocean (A)	South America N South America N		
Coast (O) Far (O) Open Ocean (O)	South America M South America N	Weddel Sea N	

Globally speaking, it is easy to notice that the occurrence of natural slicks is much higher in the Northern Hemisphere than in the Southern. In the Southern Hemisphere, apart from the northern coast of Chile, almost no surface slick has been detected, both in April and in October, close as well as far from the coast.

In the Northern Hemisphere and close to the Equator, several coastal regions (North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Galapagos Islands, Philippines) have been found where the slicks occurrence is particularly high in April. With the exception of Philippines, the activity is significantly reduced in October.

Very few surface slicks have been found in the open ocean. Only the Atlantic Ocean, both in April and October, and the Equatorial Pacific Ocean, in October, present some kind of activity. On the other hand, in semi-enclosed seas, such as the Mediterranean Sea, the North Sea, the Gulf of Mexico, the Sea of Okhotsk, the Red Sea, the Japan Sea, the slick occurrence seems to be generally higher.

No clear trend has been found related to the season in the available data sets. In some regions the number of slicks is higher in April, in others in October.

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Technical Report

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On the Occurrence of Surface Slicks in the Oceans

by

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Summary

This report contains the results of a research on the occurrence of *natural biogenic surface slicks* in different regions of the oceans. The objective was to quantitatively investigate their presence in different waters, trying to find out a relation between their occurrence and their position referred to the distance from the coast (close to the coast, far from the coast, open ocean).

The SAR images, collected during the two SIR-C/X-SAR missions in April and October 1994, have been used in the analysis, for their capabilities to detect the presence of natural slicks on the sea surface. The main characteristics of the shuttle and its technical aspects, of interest for this research, are presented in the first part of this report.

21 sites, which were more or less intensively covered by the shuttle, have been chosen all over the world: they should offer a representative picture of regions, located at different latitudes and longitudes, for the two periods in exam. A list of the chosen sites is given in chapter 4. Each site has then been briefly analyzed: a list of the "data-takes" which have been analyzed is made and a map containing the location of the found surface slicks is associated to it: a brief comment is also added.

The results of the research have been summarized in the last chapter. In the Southern Hemisphere the occurrence of natural slicks seems to be much lower than in the Northern. Some areas, such as North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Galapagos Islands, Philippines, have been found where the occurrence of natural slicks is particularly high close to land in April. The activity significantly decreases in the same regions in October, with the exception of Philippines. In the open ocean only few surface slicks have been detected, mainly in the Atlantic Ocean. On the other hand, in semi-enclosed basins their occurrence is more relevant. No clear trend has been found related to the season.

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1. Introduction

The objective of this research was to quantitatively investigate the presence of *natural biogenic surface slicks* in different regions of the oceans, trying to find out a relation between their occurrence and their position referred to the distance from the coast (close to the coast, far from the coast, open ocean).

SAR images were employed in the research. It is well known that such a radar is able to detect the presence of natural slicks on the sea surface (see Gade et al., 1997; Hovland et al., 1993, Hovland et al., 1994, Espedal et al., 1995): the signature is a dark spot corresponding to a lower backscattering return. This is due to the damping action caused by natural films on surface ripples, which are the major responsible of the radar return in SAR images (see Huehnerfuss et al., 1983a and b).

A measure of this damping effect is the damping ratio, defined as the ratio between the damping coefficient in presence a surface slicks and that of a clean sea. The damping ratio plotted as a function of the frequency has a "resonance-like" behavior according to the Marangoni theory (see Cini and Lombardini, 1978). The maximum is located in the C-band and, thus, in this band the radar contrast is the highest. It is, then, believed that this band gives the best results for the natural slicks detection. On the other hand, several laboratory experiments have shown that the radar contrast is the lowest in the L-band: therefore, in this band it might happen not to detect natural slicks, because they are confused with the wave pattern (see Gade et al., 1996).

The presence of natural slicks signatures on SAR images is also dependent on the polarization employed and on the instrument sensitivity. As a matter of fact, the VV polarization gives an higher radar return compared to that of the HH polarization: the difference is around 2 dB (see Gower et al, 1993). When the wind is low, the radar backscatter is lower and there is a possibility that the radar return is below the instrument noise threshold: in this case the image is meaningless. Operating in the VV polarization allows to have a slightly higher noise threshold.

Several experiments have shown that the best SAR configuration for detecting natural slicks employs a C-band frequency and a VV polarization.

The detection of natural slicks is hampered by other features whose signature closely resembles that of natural slicks, such as internal waves, region of low winds, oil spills, currents shears, grease ice. Usually the discrimination is possible after a more detailed observation of the image: for example, internal waves give rise to dark signatures, whose shape, narrow and aligned stripes, is typically recognizable.

On the other hand, in the case of oil spills, the signature is so similar that auxiliary data are often required, such as wind information, platform location (Hamre et al., 1996). In this research, since the amount of data examined was huge, it was not always possible to carry out such a deeper analysis, so that the discrimination was based on the authors consideration. Often these ambiguous dark spots were found close to bright spots, which are the typical signatures of ships: in this case, it was not difficult to assume that the dark spots were probably due to oil released by the boats.

Finally, it must remembered that a window of wind speed has been found (Scott, 1986) where the detection of oil slicks is possible. The lower threshold is connected to the SAR sensitivity problem explained before and is around 2-3 m/s. The higher threshold is due to the break down action caused by moderate to strong winds (> 7 m/s) on surface slicks, so that the natural films are washed down and their damping effect disappears.

In the investigation the data collected in 1994 by the two SIR-C/X-SAR missions over different oceanography sites were analyzed. The fact that this shuttle was operating

contemporary in 3 bands is helpful for the detection of natural slicks, since it allows to plot the damping ratio as a function of the frequency. However, in this research, since the amount of data was extremely high, only the data coming from a single radar have been analyzed.

21 regions located in different parts of the world were considered. The satellite coverage was more frequent in some of these areas, while it was considerably more sporadic in others: this has been, of course, taken into account when making the final considerations.

2.SIR-C/X-SAR

The SIR-C/X-SAR is the last satellite of a group of satellite launched by the NASA under the so called *Mission to Planet Earth*. Two missions of 10 days were completed at the beginning of April and October 1994: these two periods were chosen since they have relevant seasonal differences.

The shuttle was the first satellite carrying a multi-frequency radar operating simultaneously in the L, C and X band and with different polarization. Among the other things, this has allowed to validate the multi-frequency and multi-polarization imaging models developed in these last years for the different oceanographic phenomena.

The relative low altitude of the orbit, approximately 215 km, has been particularly advantageous in the oceanographic investigations, since it has increased the range of ocean waves reliably imaged by the SAR instruments compared to the other high orbit satellite. Besides, this choice allowed a slight westwards drift in the equatorial crossing longitude in the one day repeat orbit so that many sites were imaged at very different incidence angle. Finally, the daily repeat orbit has been proved to be well fit to the dynamics of most of the oceanographic phenomena.

During the second flight the shuttle was able to fly nearly the same orbit as the first flight: therefore, a significant amount of data was collected which allowed repeat interferometric SAR processing.

Around 400 sites were imaged: 19 had an higher priority (the so-called "supersites") and other 15 ("backup supersites") were chosen to substitute the firsts, if necessary. The total coverage of the shuttle during the two mission is shown in fig.1.

Figure 1: Ground coverage of the 2 missions.

2.1 The Shuttle Payload

The shuttle payload is formed by two radar: the SIR-C and the X-SAR. The main characteristics of the two are summarized in Table 1.

The SIR-C is a multi-polarization (HH, VV HV and VH), multi-frequency radar, operating in the L- ($\lambda_R = 23.5$ cm, $f_R = 1.25$ GHz) as well as in the C-band ($\lambda_R = 5.8$ cm, $f_R = 5.3$ GHz). It has been the first satellite able to transmit and receive contemporary in two different bands and to vary the transmitted and received polarization.

This was made possible employing two active phased-array antennae. The two beams were formed by hundreds of transmitter embedded in the radar antenna surface: by properly adjusting the energy of these transmitters the beam could be electronically steered without moving the antenna. Such a solution together with the roll and yaw maneuvers of the shuttle has allowed to acquire the images with an incidence angle varying from 20° to 60° , $\pm 20^{\circ}$ from the nominal position of 40° off the nadir.

Parameter	L-Band	C-Band	X-Band
Wavelength (cm)	23.5	5.8	3.1
Frequency (GHz)	1.25	5.3	9.6
Polarization	HH, VV, HV, VH	HH, VV, HV, VH	VV
Spatial Resolution (m)	13-26	13-26	10 - 20
Look-Angle	20° - 60°	20° - 60°	17° - 63°
Swath Width (km)	15×90 - 15×60	15×90 - 15×60	15×90 - 15×60
Bandwidth (MHz)	10 - 20	10 - 20	10 - 20

Table 1. SIR-C/X-SAR System Characteristics.

The X-SAR is a single polarization (VV) radar, operating in the X-band ($\lambda_R = 3.1$ cm, $f_R = 9.6$ GHz). The antenna was a planar slotted waveguide array, mounted on a support structure which was mechanically tilted in order to align the narrow, pencil-thin beam with those of the SIR-C. The incidence angles varied from 17° to 63° , $\pm 23^{\circ}$ from the nominal position.

The SIR-C and the X-SAR were synchronized in order to have identical imaging geometry, thus allowing a comparison of the radar signatures in the 3 bands. However, each radar system could also operate autonomously. The transmit bandwidth could be changed, therefore making the range resolution variable.

2.2 The noise equivalent sigma zero

The SIR-C/X-SAR was designed in order to have a sufficient system sensitivity: this is specified in terms of the noise equivalent sigma zero σ_n , defined as the surface backscattering coefficient corresponding to a signal to noise ratio equal to 1.

The planned value for an incidence angle of 50° and operating in low resolution mode are:

- - 40 dB for the L-Band
- - 35 dB for the C-Band
- - 22 dB for the X-Band.

If these values are confirmed in practice, then the threshold value of wind above which the detection is possible should increase. For example, the value of σ_n was planned to be around -27 dB for the ERS SAR (operating in the C-Band, VV polarization) leading to a wind threshold of around 3 m/s; for the RADARSAT (operating in the same band, but HH polarization) the value of σ_n was expected to be circa 2 dB higher, due to the lower return caused by operating in the horizontal polarization.

If this higher sensitivity of the SIR-C/X-SAR is confirmed than the window of wind velocities inside which the detection of natural surface slicks is possible would increase: as a matter of fact, the higher threshold value does not depend on the instrument sensitivity, but on the fact that at this high to moderate wind condition the film is washed down. On the other hand, low wind conditions are idle for the generation of surface slicks.

3. Availability of data

The analysis has been based on the images either provided by the DLR through its web site (address: <http://www.dfd.dlr.de>) or stored on the JPL CD_ROM. Both these two types of data are Survey Product: thus, they serve as quick-looks on the areas imaged by the shuttle, but they do not contain any quantitative information (for example, they are not calibrated). On the other hand, since the aim of the research was focused on retrieving statistical information about the occurrence of surface slicks, the main point was that the image quality was enough good to allow the detection of the dark spots caused by surface slicks.

The DLR site provided only X-SAR images: anyway, this band and the polarization employed (VV) can be considered suitable for the detection of natural slicks. The images have been processed before being stored in the web site: if this, from one hand, has been helpful in improving the signatures of surface features in the open ocean, on the other hand it has hampered their detection close to the coast, where the land was more often privileged at the expense of the sea. Besides, few information about the images (incidence angle, spatial resolution, date, time) were displayed.

The data on the CD-ROM contains much more technical information. On the other hand, all the images analyzed were in the L-band and a good part in the HH polarization, which is considered the worst configuration for natural slicks detection.

3.1 The Data-Takes

The SIR-C/X-SAR data have been acquired in units of so-called "data takes". These are named by the major test site. They may be thousands as well as few tens kilometers long and therefore span whole continents or very limited regions. The test sites have been monitored several times on ascending and descending orbits, with different radar parameters, like incidence angle and spatial resolution.

All test sites have been assigned a 3 character Site ID. The first character indicates the primary discipline of the investigation: C for calibration, E for ecology, G for geology, H for hydrology, M for electromagnetic theory, N for oceanography and T for targets of opportunity. The second character is used to distinguish a Supersite (S) from a Backup Supersite (B) or from a Non Supersite (any other character). The third character distinguishes between different site coverage.

4. The choice of the different sites

The 21 sites were selected trying to cover the most different parts of the ocean, according to the SIR-C/X-SAR coverage. The attempt was to have the most homogeneous distribution as possible for the different latitudes and longitudes: except from the regions at high latitudes in the Southern Hemisphere, the purpose has been reached.

In some areas, such as in the mid latitude regions for both Southern and Northern Hemisphere, several different coastal sites were covered by the SIR-C/X-SAR: in this case, one had to make a choice. It can be that this has favored sites which were then discovered to have an insignificant biogenic activity at the expense of other sites which might have an higher activity. But this choice was made in order to have a treatable number of data.

Unfortunately, some sites were not sufficiently covered by the space shuttle, so that the results need to be further verified. On the other hand, other were covered more frequently, so that the total amount of images was huge: in this case, only a part of the available data takes has been selected, according to the criteria of having the data covering repeated orbit and distributed among several days.

The 21 sites, divided according to their latitudinal position, are listed in the tables below.

Table 2: High Latitude Sites, Northern Hemisphere.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
1. Alaska Sea	45 N -> 65 N	130 W -> 160 W
2. North Atlantic	40 N -> 60 N	10 W -> 45 W
3. North Sea	50 N -> 60 N	5 W -> 25 E
4. Okhotsk Sea	45 N -> 60 N	140 E -> 165 E

Table 3: Mid Latitude Sites, Northern Hemisphere.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
5. Gulf Stream	25 N -> 40 N	65 W -> 80 W
6. Mediterranean Sea	30 N -> 45 N	5 E -> 25 E
7. Japan Sea	25 N -> 45 N	120 E -> 140 E
8. Hawaii	10 N -> 30 N	145 W -> 165 W
9. Mexico Gulf	10 N -> 35 N	75 W -> 95 W

Table 4: Equatorial Sites.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
10. Red Sea	10 N -> 25 N	35 E -> 45 E
11. Pacific Survey	10 S -> 15 N	140 W -> 170 W
12. Galapagos Islands	10 S -> 10 N	80 W -> 100 W
13. Gulf of Guinea	5 S -> 5 N	15 W -> 5 E
14. Indian Ocean	0 N -> 10 N	75 E -> 85 E
15. Philippines	10 S -> 25 N	110 E -> 130 E

Table 5: Mid Latitude Sites, Southern Hemisphere.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
16. Brazil	20 S -> 5 N	30 W -> 50 W
17. Chile	15 S -> 35 S	65 W -> 80 W
18. South Africa	10 S -> 50 S	10 E -> 50 E
19. Australian Current	25 S -> 40 S	150 E -> 160 E

Table 6: High Latitude Sites, Southern Hemisphere.

	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
20. South America	40 S -> 60 S	55 W -> 85 W
21. Weddel Sea	50 S -> 60 S	0 E -> 20 E

The map below shows the location of the sites.

5. The 21 sites

In the following paragraph each site is analyzed in details.

First, all the data-takes are listed with their main technical characteristics: the date and the time, the number, the name of the location, the ID code, the polarization, the incidence angle, the number of quick-looks analyzed. The data takes from DLR can be recognized because they are from the X-SAR (X-band, VV polarization), while those from JPL are from the SIR-C, L band.

After the list of data-takes, a brief comment is made concerning the site coverage and its slick activity in April and October. Finally, the map with the locations of natural surface slicks is attached.

Site #1 - Alaska Gulf

10/04	18:26	022.14	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	36.8	15
	19:58	023.02	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	36.6	11
12/04	19:21	055.02	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	32.9	15
13/10	19:01	071.02	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	30.9	16
15/04	18:20	103.01	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	L-HH	28.6	21
16/04	16:27	118.02	NE Pacific Ocean A2	N37	X-VV	29.9	22
18/04	14:13	149.02	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	L-HH	36.1	21
01/10	18:37	022.14	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	37.2	15
	20:09	023.20	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	36.9	15
02/10	19:52	039.20	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	35.1	8
04/10	19:12	071.10	NE Pacific Ocean AO	N35	X-VV	30.9	5
06/10	17:10	102.20	NE Pacific Ocean A2	N37	X-VV	39.8	15
07/10	16:27	118.10	Top Orbit/Interferometry	GF2	X-VV	47.2	10
08/10	16:19	134.10	Top Orbit/Interferometry	GF2	X-VV	47.3	11
09/10	15:56	150.10	Top Orbit/Interferometry	GF2	X-VV	47.3	10

April: no surface slicks have been detected.

October: two regions, presenting a low activity, have been found in the same day (data takes 022.14 and 023.20), at a certain distance from the coast. However, in the following days no other surface slicks have been detected. There is one suspicious signature in data takes 149.02, which could be due to natural slicks. No activity at all has been found close to the coast.

Site #2 - North Atlantic

10/04	14:05	019.02	EN Atlantic A	NS5	X-VV	39.2	33
11/04	07:40	031.01	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	39.7	15
12/04	07:21	047.01	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	31.0	23
13/04	07:02	063.01	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	22.1	16
14/04	06:42	079.01	EN Atlantic C	NS7	X-VV	24.7	20
15/04	06:23	095.03	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	30.0	11
16/04	12:08	115.05	EN Atlantic E	NS9	X-VV	24.0	32
17/04	05:41	127.01	EN Atlantic F	NSX	X-VV	20.8	15
18/04	05:18	143.01	EN Atlantic G	NSY	X-VV	28.0	20
01/10	14:16	019.20	EN Atlantic A	NS5	X-VV	29.8	33
02/10	07:51	031.10	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	39.3	14
03/10	07:32	047.11	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	30.8	35
04/10	07:13	063.10	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	21.3	16
05/10	06:55	079.10	EN Atlantic C	NS7	X-VV	24.6	11
06/10	06:34	095.30	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	30.2	12
07/10	12:20	115.50	EN Atlantic E	NS9	X-VV	27.0	35
08/10	05:51	127.00	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	39.7	13
09/10	05:28	143.00	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	39.8	12
10/10	05:25	159.00	EN Atlantic D	NS8	X-VV	39.8	11

The North Atlantic was marked as an oceanographical supersite and, thus, several data takes have been taken.

April: a big number of surface slicks have been detected, though their presence is not constant during the period. As a matter of fact, no activity at all is found from April 13th to 15th and in the last two days. This may be due to the strong wind which may have blown for some days and been absent in others. The surface slicks seem to be concentrated in well defined regions: mainly between 19° and 26° West and 43° and 47° North and around 30° West and 50° North;

October: the activity seems to be even higher than in April, though again not constant. As a matter of fact, the last five days of October (from 6th to 10th) no surface slicks at all have been revealed. Also in this case the activity seems to be concentrated in a well defined region located between 17° and 26° West and 45° and 48 North, which is circa the same area of April.

Site # 3 - North Sea

10/04	09:35	016.12	Stauning, Denmark (1)	G65	X-VV	30.1	14
11/04	10:49	033.05	Stauning, Denmark (1)	G65	X-VV	36.9	16
12/04	07:21	047.01	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	31.0	17
13/04	07:06	063.02	North Sea A1	NBB	X-VV	35.3	11
14/04	08:20	080.03	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	40.3	18
15/04	07:53	096.03	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	48.5	14
16/04	07:33	112.02	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	29.9	20
17/04	05:45	127.02	Thetford, England	E66	X-VV	46.5	30
01/10	09:46	016.12	Stauning, Denmark (1)	G65	X-VV	30.1	11
02/10	11:00	033.50	Stauning, Denmark (1)	G65	X-VV	36.8	17
03/10	07:32	047.11	EN Atlantic B	NS6	X-VV	30.8	6
04/10	07:18	063.10	North Sea A1	NBB	X-VV	38.3	20
05/10	08:30	080.10	North Sea Slick	N45	X-VV	44.3	32
06/10	08:05	096.20	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	44.0	10
07/10	07:45	112.20	North Sea A0	NBA	X-VV	43.2	29
08/10	07:28	128.20	Rugen Island, Germany	H02	X-VV	46.3	27
09/10	07:05	144.20	Rugen Island, Germany	H02	X-VV	45.7	40
10/10	06:42	160.20	Rugen Island, Germany	H02	X-VV	46.2	28

April: several surface slicks have been detected, especially on the west side of the Danish coast, both close as well as far from the coast: a good activity is also present close to the German coast. These region is known to have strong mesoscale processes, called eddies, which in fact have been detected (data takes 047.01 and 112.02): they can give rise to natural surface slicks, with a vortex shape, following the eddy orbital movement direction (see Dokken and Wahl, 1996; Johannessen, 1993). Besides, the North Sea is highly naval trafficked and there are several oil platforms, located especially close to the German coast: for this region it is subjected to an high degree of oil pollution. Few slicks, closely resembling to natural slicks, have been detected, which have been assumed to be caused by oil spills. In most of these cases the dark spot was associated to bright spots representing oil platforms or ships.

October: no surface slicks have been detected in the first 7 days, while afterwards a good activity was found, concentrated far from the coast. Again, some oil spills were detected.

Site # 4 - Sea of Okhotsk

11/04	00:25	026.04	Karymsky, Kamchatka	G62	X-VV	35.3	18
11/04	22:35	041.02	Tolbechik, Kamchatka	G34	X-VV	29.9	21
12/04	00:05	042.02	Karymsky, Kamchatka	G62	X-VV	32.2	29
12/04	01:38	043.03	Sea of Okhotsk A0	N48	X-VV	26.8	19
13/04	01:19	059.02	Sea of Okhotsk A2	N50	X-VV	26.8	25
13/04	23:27	074.03	Sea of Okhotsk A2	N50	L-VV	28.1	13
15/04	22:46	106.20	Sea of Okhotsk A2	N50	L-VV	28.4	13
17/04	22:05	138.02	Bezymienny, Kamchatka	G40	X-VV	38.4	21
01/10	00:53	010.10	Karymsky, Kamchatka	G62	L-VH	41.1	18
03/10	22:26	057.20	Tolbechik, Kamchatka	G34	L-VH	34.2	16
06/10	19:56	104.30	Kliuchevskai, Kamchatka	G08	L-HH	28.3	13
07/10	20:51	121.10	Kliuchevskai2, Kamchatka	GCI	L-VV	31.3	20
09/10	20:06	153.10	Kliuchevskai2, Kamchatka	GCI	L-VV	31.3	20

April: the region was mainly covered by ice, especially close to the Khabarovsk Kray coast. Here several dark areas have been detected, probably due to grease ice. Only very few natural slicks have been found, mainly close to the Kamchatka peninsula.

October: in this case the ice was not yet formed. Many surface slicks have been detected, particularly in the stripe between 54° and 57° North, far from the coast.

Site # 5 - Gulf Stream

10/04	18:39	022.03	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	46.4	15
12/04	18:01	054.02	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	L-HH	32.8	16
13/04	17:34	070.01	Gulf Stream A1	NS1	L-VV	33.6	10
14/04	17:23	086.05	Gulf Stream A1	NS1	L-HH	38.6	12
16/04	16:42	118.07	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	L-VV	25.6	15
17/04	16:21	134.05	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	30.0	23
01/10	18:50	022.30	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	36.5	14
03/10	18:12	054.30	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	50.7	34
05/10	17:34	086.50	Gulf Stream A1	NS1	L-HH	21.4	12
07/10	16:55	118.33	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	39.5	15
08/10	16:32	134.33	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	39.5	15
09/10	16:09	150.33	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	39.5	15
10/10	15:46	166.52	Gulf Stream A0	NS0	X-VV	27.2	15

April: the activity is not constant, so that there is an alternation of days having a medium activity with others showing no activity at all. Besides, it is not possible to define any region where the surface slicks particularly occur; however, they have not been detected close to the coast.

October: far from the coast the activity seems to be more intensive than in April, while it remains null close to it. Like in April, the surface slicks are not located in a precise area.

Site # 6 - Mediterranean Sea

10/04	12:43	018.22	Matera, Italy	CB1	L-HH	16.4	11
11/04	12:25	034.32	Matera, Italy	CB1	V-HH	32.6	12
13/04	11:47	066.42	Matera, Italy	CB1	V-HH	50.0	14
17/04	02:36	125.02	Matera, Italy	CB1	L-HH	19.1	10
18/04	02:20	141.12	Matera, Italy	CB1	L-HH	23.3	7
19/04	01:57	157.00	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	L-HH	55.9	12
20/04	01:34	173.10	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	L-HH	57.0	10
01/10	05:10	013.11	Central Greece	T83	X-VV	34.2	4
01/10	12:54	018.22	Matera, Italy	CB1	X-VV	19.1	18
04/10	04:12	061.10	Matera, Italy	CB1	X-VV	22.8	13
04/10	11:58	066.32	Strait of Sicily	N57	X-VV	51.1	13
07/10	10:58	114.50	Monastir, Tunisia	G91	X-VV	57.5	11
08/10	02:52	125.10	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	X-VV	47.6	22
09/10	02:29	141.10	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	X-VV	47.6	19
10/10	02:06	157.10	Mt.Etna, Italy	TI6	X-VV	47.6	20

April: many surface slicks have been found close to the coast, spread on several areas; far from it the activity seems to be negligible.

October: the activity is still good close to the coast. Far from it, several natural slicks have been found, particularly in the Sicilian Channel.

Mediterranean Sea - April

Mediterranean Sea - October

Site # 7 - Japan Sea

10/04	05:19	013.03	Japan A0	N66	X-VV	27.2	26
11/04	05:01	029.05	Japan C3	N79	X-VV	45.9	42
12/04	04:43	045.03	Japan A1	N67	X-VV	36.6	17
13/04	04:23	061.04	Japan A0	N66	X-VV	27.8	19
14/04	04:05	077.04	Japan A4	N70	X-VV	25.7	20
01/10	05:30	013.30	Japan A0	N66	L-HH	29.1	17
					X-VV	27.7	1
02/10	05:12	029.50	Japan A2	N68	L-HH	49.9	26
03/10	04:53	045.40	Japan A1	N67	L-HH	40.3	21
04/10	04:34	061.40	Japan A0	N66	X-VV	26.9	24
05/10	04:16	077.40	Japan A4	N70	L-HH	27.7	15

April: a good activity is constantly present close to the Japan coast. Far from it it is negligible, with the exception of April 11th, when some surface slicks have been found in the region centered around 40°N and 132°E.

October: while close to the coast the situation is similar to that of April, far from it many more surface slicks have been detected, both in the Japan Sea as well as in the Pacific Ocean.

Japan Sea – April

Japan Sea – October

Site # 8 - Hawaii

12/04	14:37	052.01	Hawaii	BG0	X-VV	49.5	11
13/04	14:17	068.00	Hawaii	GB0	X-VV	56.7	40
16/04	13:16	116.01	Blue Hawaii	N04	X-VV	26.9	21
17/04	12:55	132.02	Blue Hawaii	N04	X-VV	26.9	21
18/04	12:33	148.00	Blue Hawaii	N04	X-VV	35.4	21
03/10	14:48	052.10	Kilauca, Hawaii	GB0	X-VV	49.3	16
04/10	14:28	068.00	Kilauca, Hawaii	GB0	X-VV	56.6	40
07/10	13:28	116.10	Blue Hawaii	N04	L-HH	29.3	17
08/10	22:29	138.40	Pu'u O'o, Hawaii	G10	X-VV	58.5	25
10/10	21:43	170.40	Pu'u O'o, Hawaii	G10	X-VV	58.5	22

April: no activity at all.

October: no activity at all.

Site # 9 - Gulf of Mexico

11/04	19:53	039.04	Gulf of Mexico 1	N07	X-VV	39.8	22
12/04	19:35	055.05	Gulf of Mexico 0	N06	X-VV	39.8	7
13/04	09:54	065.02	Gulf of Mexico	N06	X-VV	27.4	10
	19:16	071.05	Gulf of Mexico 3	N09	X-VV	44.8	6
14/04	09:30	081.00	Chulchece, Yucatan Mex	E58	X-VV	24.5	17
02/10	20:02	039.40	Gulf of Mexico 1	N07	X-VV	39.8	36
04/10	19:26	071.50	Gulf of Mexico 3	N09	X-VV	44.7	29
07/10	18:23	119.30	20MHz D/L over N.Amer	GF8	X-VV	47.3	21
09/10	17:37	151.30	20MHz D/L over N.Amer	GF8	X-VV	47.3	20

The Gulf of Mexico is known for presenting several oil seepages, whose signatures on SAR images closely resembles those of natural slicks: some attention must then be paid in order to not confuse the two surface features. Besides, several images contained bright spots, since this region has an high naval traffic: therefore, some dark spots may be due to oil spills.

April: the activity is mainly concentrated far from the coast, in the region centered at 26⁰N and 87⁰W. However, it is never particularly high, though constant for all the days. One slick have been detected close to Cuba coast (data takes 055.05).

October: the situation is mainly identical to April, though far from the coast the activity is slightly more intense and seems to be more spread.

Gulf of Mexico – April

Gulf of Mexico – October

Site # 10 - Red Sea

10/04	01:53	011.01	Saudi Arabia D(1) 4	GOX	X-VV	35.0	3
11/04	01:35	027.01	Saudi Arabia A(1) 0	GB4	X-VV	42.4	3
13/04	00:56	059.01	Saudi Arabia C(2) 4	GB5	X-VV	46.5	4
14/04	00:33	075.04	Mabira, Uganda	E33	X-VV	28.8	4
15/04	00:18	091.03	Saudi Arabia D(1) 2	GB8	X-VV	54.6	3
15/04	23:58	107.03	Saudi Arabia D(1) 2	GB8	L-HH	54.6	4
01/10	02:04	011.10	Saudi Arabia C(1) 4	GOX	L-HH	44.1	3
04/10	01:05	059.62	Saudi Arabia C(2) 4	GB5	L-HH	43.2	5
05/10	00:44	075.40	Mabira, Uganda	E33	L-HH	29.3	4
07/10	00:09	107.30	Saudi Arabia D(1) 2	GB8	L-HH	57.6	
09/10	22:50	154.90	Konjoke Res. Ctr. Rwanda	T03	X-VV	25.1	6

The region has been covered for a sufficient number of days (5) both in April and October. Unfortunately, the data takes were taken across, and not along, the Red Sea, often in its most narrow part. Therefore, only few images were available.

April: the slick activity is quite high, both close as well as far from the coast.

October: same as April.

Red Sea – April

Red Sea – October

Site # 11 - Equatorial Pacific Ocean

10/04	02:31	011.04	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX3	X-VV	28.4	29
13/04	12:41	066.09	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX6	X-VV	27.8	27
14/04	21:58	089.03	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX9	X-VV	27.3	26
15/04	23:06	106.03	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NXD	X-VV	27.3	29
17/04	09:51	129.09	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX9	X-VV	26.9	29
01/10	02:41	011.40	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX3	X-VV	26.8	26
02/10	12:02	133.20	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX8	X-VV	26.8	31
04/10	12:52	066.20	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX6	X-VV	27.4	31
05/10	23:17	106.40	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NXD	X-VV	26.9	32
06/10	09:16	162.00	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NXG	X-VV	26.9	31
10/10	01:29	075.70	Equatorial Pacific Survey	NX3	X-VV	33.2	33

April: no surface slicks have been detected, except from the data takes 106.03.

October: the activity seems to be highly intensive, though not constant through all the days. This may suggest that in the days where no surface slicks have been found the wind was too strong.

Equatorial Pacific Ocean – April

Equatorial Pacific Ocean – October

Site # 12 - Galapagos Islands

11/04	21:29	040.05	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	21.0	28
14/04	20:32	088.06	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	34.0	11
15/04	20:11	104.07	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	46.0	18
17/04	19:28	136.03	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	52.4	40
02/10	21:40	040.50	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	22.4	22
04/10	21:02	072.70	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	22.8	20
05/10	20:43	088.60	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	46.0	14
06/10	20:22	104.70	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	53.3	16
07/10	20:02	120.70	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	53.9	21
08/10	19:39	136.70	Galapagos Islands	GS1	X-VV	54.0	18

April: there is an excellent activity close to the islands, while no surface slicks have been detected in the open ocean.

October: no surface slick has been detected.

Galapagos Islands – April

Site # 13 - Gulf of Guinea

11/04	15:28	036.07	Sahel 0	EX3	L-HH	36.5	5
12/04	15:15	052.05	Sahel	EX4	L-HH	36.3	4
17/04	13:29	132.08	Sahel	EXD	L-HH	37.0	12
02/10	15:39	036.70	Sahel	EX3	X-VV	34.9	6
03/10	15:26	052.50	Sahel	EX4	X-VV	35.4	4
07/10	14:02	116.50	Sahel	EXB	X-VV	35.3	6
08/10	13:39	132.30	W.America fix 45	GF7	X-VV	44.7	13
09/10	02:19	140.90	Tilemsi, Sahara Mali	G53	L-VV	46.8	5
10/10	01:56	156.90	Tilemsi, Sahara Mali	G53	L-VV	47.1	7

The coverage is limited to the coastal region and, besides, is quite poor in April.

April: no surface slicks.

October: no surface slicks.

Site # 14 - Indian Ocean

08/10	07:28	128.20	Rugen Island, Germany	HO2	X-VV	46.3	18
09/10	07:05	144.20	Rugen Island, Germany	HO2	X-VV	45.7	25
10/10	06:42	160.20	Rugen Island, Germany	HO2	X-VV	46.2	3

In April this region was not covered by any data take. Also in October, however, the coverage is limited, both concerning the number of the days (only 3) as well as the distance from the coast.

October: few surface slicks, located approximately in the same region (the only one imaged by the shuttle), at a certain distance from the coast.

Site # 15 - Philippines

12/04	06:20	046.03	Western Pacific 11	CSK	X-VV	57.5	57
14/04	05:39	078.03	Pinatubo, Philippines	G98	X-VV	51.3	28
16/04	04:57	110.03	Western Pacific 3	CSC	X-VV	55.3	59
08/10	04:38	126.30	Pinatubo, Philippines	G98	X-VV	29.6	30
09/10	04:16	142.30	Pinatubo, Philippines	G98	X-VV	29.6	30
10/10	03:53	158.30	Pinatubo, Philippines	G98	X-VV	29.6	30

Though only few days have been considered, the results can be considered significant.

April: good activity, concentrated around the Philippines: no surface slick has been found in the open ocean.

October: close to the coast the activity is even more intensive than before and is extended to Indonesia; far from it it is still negligible.

Philippines Sea— April

Philippines Sea— October

Site # 16 - Brazil

14/04	17:35	086.06	Bebedouro, Brazil	HSI	X-VV	47.3	16
15/04	17:14	102.06	Bebedouro, Brazil	HSI	X-VV	53.2	10
30/09	19:19	006.30	Bebedouro, Brazil	HSI	X-VV	45.8	25
02/10	18:47	038.60	Bahia, Brazil	T33	L-HH	51.0	9
05/10	17:46	086.60	Bebedouro, Brazil	HSI	X-VV	47.1	14
07/10	17:04	118.50	South America fix a45	GF3	L-VV	47.1	18
09/10	16:18	150.50	South America fix a45	GF3	L-VV	47.1	18
10/10	15:55	166.80	South America fix a45	GF3	L-VV	47.1	18

The coverage is quite poor in April (only 2 days) and limited to coastal areas.

April: no surface slick has been detected.

October: the data are contradictory, since in some days there is some activity, while in others no surface slick has been found. However, the global activity is very low.

Site # 17 - North Chile

10/04	21:57	021.08	Cerro Aroncagua, Argent	GON	X-VV	49.7	7
12/04	07:01	046.05	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	X-VV	28.8	6
14/04	06:21	078.06	Amason Calibration	CXH	X-VV	28.8	12
	20:40	088.07	San Juan, Argentina	GOA	X-VV	41.4	7
15/04	06:03	094.07	Menaus CSAP, Brazil	ES2	L-HH	26.3	7
16/04	05:42	110.05	Menaus Cabakiane, Brazil	ES1	L-HH	27.4	6
18/04	05:00	142.05	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	L-HH	49.9	4
30/09	22:26	008.70	San Juan, Argentina	GOA	X-VV	37.3	7
01/10	22:08	024.80	Cerro Aroncagua, Argent	GON	X-VV	49.6	7
03/10	07:12	046.50	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	X-VV	30.1	6
05/10	06:32	078.60	Amason Calibration	CXH	X-VV	30.4	12
	20:51	088.70	San Juan, Argentina	GOA	X-VV	41.1	6
07/10	05:53	110.50	Menaus Cabakiane, Brazil	ES1	X-VV	30.9	11
09/10	05:09	142.80	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	X-VV	43.8	8
10/10	04:46	158.80	Cherena, Bolivia	GOK	X-VV	43.9	6

The coverage is mainly limited to coastal regions.

April: several slicks have been found close to the coast, around 20°S.

October: as in April, the activity seems to be limited to the same coastal regions.

Site # 18 - South Africa

11/04	15:43	036.08	Roter Kamm, Namibia 1	G68	L-HH	25.5	8
13/04	13:33	067.07	Kruger National Park, SA	E23	X-VV	55.2	6
17/04	21:29	137.07	Southern Africa	N53	L-VV	38.6	13
02/10	00:05	025.50	Mozambique Channel	TB3	X-VV	48.3	19
04/10	13:44	067.70	Kruger National Park, SA	E13	X-VV	55.1	6
06/10	22:23	105.90	Southern Africa	N53	L-HH	28.8	43
07/10	11:13	114.60	Mozambique Channel	TB3	L-VV	50.7	10
09/10	21:17	153.60	Southern Africa	N53	L-HH	28.4	34
10/10	11:19	163.50	Sahel	EX2	X-VV	45.3	25

April: no surface slick has been detected.

October: the data cover a wider region than in April. In the area imaged also in April there is no surface slick. Some are, instead, found in the North-West coast of Mozambique, at latitudes close to Equator.

South Africa – October

Site # 19 - Australian Current

11/04	06:51	030.03	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	37.0	12
12/04	06:32	046.04	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	37.2	9
14/04	05:53	078.05	Australian Current	NO2	X-VV	26.8	11
18/04	03:00	141.07	Norfolk Island,Austr.	N43	X-VV	54.4	19
20/04	03:46	174.40	Sydney, Australia	T18	L-VV	31.3	9
02/10	07:02	030.40	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	37.3	12
03/10	06:43	046.40	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	37.2	19
05/10	06:04	078.40	Australian Current	NO2	L-VV	28.8	11
08/10	04:57	126.40	Australian Fox a45	GFI	X-VV	45.2	30
09/10	04:34	142.40	Australian Fox a45	GFI	X-VV	45.3	30
10/10	04:11	158.40	Australian Fox a45	GFI	X-VV	45.3	30

April: no surface slicks.

October: no surface slicks.

Site # 20 - South America

11/04	23:13	041.05	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	44.2	14
12/04	05:22	045.06	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	48.8	19
13/04	05:04	061.07	Cerro Cumbre	GSK	X-VV	47.6	6
14/04	04:45	077.07	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	53.4	5
17/04	21:12	137.03	Puerto Aisen	GSJ	X-VV	39.5	17
18/04	03:22	141.09	Cerro Cumbre	GSK	X-VV	54.8	4
01/10	00:01	009.40	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	54.2	12
	06:11	013.60	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	X-VV	38.0	11
	23:42	025.30	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	L-HH	49.7	15
02/10	23:24	041.50	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	L-HH	32.5	12
03/10	22:46	057.50	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	L-HH	39.8	12
04/10	05:15	061.70	Cerro Cumbre	GSK	X-VV	48.4	5
	22:46	073.30	Cerro Laukaru	GSL	L-HH	32.5	11
06/10	04:36	093.70	Cerro Cumbre	GSK	L-HH	65.3	6
07/10	04:15	109.70	Puerto Aisen	GSJ	X-VV	48.3	6

April: no surface slicks.

October: a good activity is found far from the coast in October 3rd and 7th. The other days it looks like the wind is quite strong.

Site # 21 - Weddel Sea

01/10	20:51	023.60	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	22.8	24
02/10	20:32	039.90	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	20.3	33
03/10	20:13	055.80	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	30.4	31
04/10	19:54	071.80	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	29.9	21
06/10	19:14	103.80	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	28.7	31
07/10	18:53	119.50	Weddel Sea	N59	X-VV	22.8	35

Coverage: no data in April; good in October (6 days).

October: in the first days the area is mainly covered by ice, while in the last two data takes its extension is significantly reduced. No surface slick has been detected. Some attention must be paid to some dark features which closely resemble to natural slick, but which are more likely grease ice.

6. Final Results

The results of the investigation are summarized in the tables below. For each site a letter has been assigned, when possible, referring to its slick activity: N for negligible, VL for very low, L for low, M for medium, H for high, VH for very high. Of course, this classification is subjective, but the author believes this gives the best picture of the situation. A more statistical approach, for example based on the percentage of images containing natural slicks, is not applicable in this case: as a matter of fact, the degree of activity may vary considerably in different images and this must be taken in to account.

Besides, some images may contain only one or few dark spots, whose origin is not clear: they may be due to biogenic activity, but they may be also caused by man-made pollution. Their discrimination is not always possible and a more detailed analysis requires wind information and other means of help which are unusable for such an exhaustive research.

For high latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	Alaska Gulf N	North Sea VH	Sea of Okhotsk L
Far (A)	Alaska Gulf N	North Sea VH	Sea of Okhotsk N
Open Ocean (A)		Atlantic Ocean M	
Coast (O)	Alaska Gulf N	North Sea L	Sea of Okhotsk VL
Far (O)	Alaska Gulf VL	North Sea M	Sea of Okhotsk VH
Open Ocean (O)		Atlantic Ocean H	

For mid latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	Gulf of Mexico VL Gulf Stream N	Mediterranean Sea H	Japan Sea M
Far (A)	Gulf of Mexico M Gulf Stream M	Mediterranean Sea VL	Japan Sea M
Open Ocean (A)	Hawaii VL		
Coast (O)	Gulf of Mexico N Gulf Stream N	Mediterranean Sea M	Japan Sea M
Far (O)	Gulf of Mexico M Gulf Stream H	Mediterranean Sea VH	Japan Sea VH
Open Ocean (O)	Hawaii N		

For the Equator regions::

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	Galapagos Islands VH	Red Sea M Guinea N	Philippines H
Far (A)	Galapagos Islands	Red Sea M	Philippines VL

	VL		
Open Ocean (A)	Pacific Ocean VL Galapagos Islands N		Philippines N
Coast (O)	Galapagos Islands N	Red Sea M Guinea N	Indian Ocean N Philippines VH
Far (O)	Galapagos Islands N	Red Sea M	Indian Ocean VL Philippines VL
Open Ocean (O)	Pacific Ocean M Galapagos Islands N		Philippines N

For mid latitudes in the Southern Hemisphere:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	Brazil N North Chile H	South Africa N	Australian Current N
Far (A)	Brazil N North Chile L		Australian Current N
Open Ocean (A)			
Coast (O)	Brazil N North Chile H	South Africa N	Australian Current N
Far (O)	Brazil VL North Chile L	South Africa N	Australian Current N
Open Ocean (O)			

For high latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere:

	WEST		EAST
Coast (A)	South America N		
Far (A)	South America N		
Open Ocean (A)			
Coast (O)	South America M		
Far (O)	South America N		
Open Ocean (O)		Weddel Sea N	

Globally speaking, it is easy to notice that the occurrence of natural slicks is much higher in the Northern Hemisphere than in the Southern; here, apart from the northern coast of Chile, almost no surface slick has been detected, both in April and in October, close as well as far from the coast.

In the Northern Hemisphere and close to the Equator several coastal regions (North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Galapagos Islands, Philippines) have been found where the slicks

occurrence is particularly high in April; with the exception of Philippines, the activity is significantly reduced in October.

Very few surface slicks have been found in the open ocean; only the Atlantic Ocean, both in April and October, and the Equatorial Pacific Ocean, in October, present some kind of activity. On the other hand, in semi-enclosed seas, such as the Mediterranean Sea, the North Sea, the Gulf of Mexico, the Sea of Okhotsk, the Red Sea, the Japan Sea, the slick occurrence seems to be generally higher.

No clear trend has been found related to the season: in some regions the number of slicks is higher in April, in others in October.

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